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DUAL -SERVER PUBLIC KEY AUTHENTICATED ENCRYPTION WITH KEYWORD SEARCH

1. ABSTRACT: The development of cloud computing greatly raises the utilization of computing and storage resources, and the users' access to data also becomes more convenient. However, the openness of cloud computing environments also make user data security face greater challenges, and this now becomes one of the main problems hindering the development of cloud computing technology. This paper presents a secure cloud storage system based on attribute encryption that supports cipher text retrieval. Users first request an attribute key from the trusted center, then outsource encrypted private data to the cloud server. Authorized users generate keyword traps with attribute keys that allow them to search for cloud-encrypted data only if the authorized user's attributes satisfy the specified access control tree. Security analysis shows that the system can effectively protect user privacy and data security. Performance analysis shows that the system has high efficiency. Data stores and cloud services are typically accessed using a client-server paradigm wherein the client runs as part of an application process which is trying to access the data store or cloud service. This paper presents the design and implementation of enhanced clients for improving both the functionality and performance of applications accessing data stores or cloud services. Our enhanced clients can improve performance via multiple types of caches, encrypt data for providing confidentiality before sending information to a server, and compress data for reducing the size of data transfers. Our clients can perform data analysis to allow applications to more effectively use cloud services. They also provide both synchronous and asynchronous interfaces. An asynchronous interface allows an application program to access a data store or cloud service and continue execution before receiving a response which can significantly improve performance. We present a Universal Data Store Manager (UDSM) which allows an application.

KEY WORD : CLOUD, DESIGN,SYSTEM,APPLICATION

INTRODUCTION: **Cloud computing** is the use of computing resources (hardware and software) that are delivered as a service over a network (typically the Internet). The name comes from the use of a cloud-shaped symbol as an abstraction for the complex infrastructure it contains in system diagrams. Cloud computing entrusts remote services with a user's data, software and computation. The cloud providers manage the infrastructure and platforms on which the applications run. End users access cloud-based applications through a web browser or a light-weight desktop or mobile app while the business software and user's data are stored on servers at a remote location. cloud computing allows enterprises to get their applications up and running faster, with improved manageability and less maintenance, and enables IT to more rapidly adjust resources to meet fluctuating and unpredictable business demand.

SYSTEM STUDY : In the system testing the whole system is tested for interface between each modules and program units are tested and recorded. This testing is done with sample data. The securities, communication between interfaces are tested System testing is actually a series of different tests whose primary purpose is to fully exercise the computer based system although each test has a different purpose all work to verify that all system elements properly integrated and perform allocate function.

EXISTING SYSTEM : As data generation is far outpacing data storage it proves costly for small firms to frequently update their hardware whenever additional data is created. Also maintaining the storages can be a difficult task. It transmitting the file across the network to the client can consume heavy bandwidths. The problem is further complicated by the fact that the owner of the data may be a small device, like a PDA (personal digital assist) or a mobile phone, which have limited CPU power, battery power and communication bandwidth.

INPUT DESIGN Asking the user about the format required by them tests the output generated by the system under consideration .It can be done in two ways, One on screen and other on printer format. The output format on the screen is found to be correct as the format designed n system test.

FILE DESIGN: Technical Feasibility assesses the current resources and technology, which are required to accomplish user requirement in the software within the allocated time and For this, the software development team ascertains whether the current resources and technology can be upgraded or added in the software to accomplish specified user requirements.

ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM:

- Apart from reduction in storage costs data outsourcing to the cloud also helps in reducing the maintenance.
- Avoiding local storage of data.
- By reducing the costs of storage, maintenance and personnel.
- It reduces the chance of losing data by hardware failures.
- Not cheating the owner.

DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

LEVEL 0:

LEVEL 1:

LEVEL 2:

LEVEL 3:

MODULES:

The system is proposed to have the following modules along with functional requirements.

1. Data encryption and uploading
2. Data downloading and decryption

Encryption evolution management

CONCLUSION : We presented the construction of an efficient PDP scheme for distributed cloud storage. Based on homomorphism verifiable response and hash index hierarchy, we have proposed a cooperative PDP scheme to support dynamic scalability on multiple storage servers. We also showed that our scheme provided all security properties required by zero knowledge interactive proof system, so that it can resist various attacks even if it is deployed as a public audit service in clouds. Furthermore, we optimized the probabilistic query and periodic verification to improve the audit performance. Our experiments clearly demonstrated that our approaches only introduce a small amount of computation and communication overheads. Therefore, our solution can be treated as a new candidate for data integrity verification in outsourcing data storage systems

BOOKS :

Alex Homer , '**Professional VB.NET 1.1**', 2004 Edition, Wrox Publications

- Clayton crooks II '**Learning Visual Basic .Net Through Applications**'
- Roger S Pressman, '**Software Engineering**', 2000 Edition, Dreamtech Publications
- Steven Holzner, '**Visual Basic.NET Black Book**', 2003 Edition, Dreamtech Publications
- A.Keyton Weissinger ,"**ASP IN A NUTSHELL**",Shroff Publishers and distributors
Pvt.Ltd,February 1999
- A.Russel Jones, "**ASP.NET Complete Reference**", Sybex Publications, February 18,2002
- DATABASE SYSTEM CONCEPTS, Henry F.Korth, Megraw-Hill, Third Edition, 1997.
- Steven Holzner, '**C#.NET Black Book**', 2003 Edition, Dreamtech Publications
- SQL SERVER HIGH AVAILABILITY, Paul Bertucci, Sams publishing, First Edition, 2004.
[5].

SOFTWARE ENGINEERING ONCEPT,Richared E.Fairly Tata Megraw-Hill
Publications, Third Edition, 1997.

WEBSITES

1. <http://www.C#corner.net>
2. <http://www.w3schools.com/asp.net>
3. <http://asp.net-tutorial.com>
4. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/asp.net>
5. www.msdn.microsoft.com

6. www.vbcity.com

7. www.vbdotnetheaven.com

8. www.codeproject.com

9. www.dotnetjohn.com